

LANGUAGE TEACHING MATERIALS AND LEARNER MOTIVATION AS IMPORTANT FACTORS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Annotation: One of the most crucial elements in learning a foreign language is the learner's motivation, and the actions of teaching and learning a language are greatly influenced by the language teaching materials. As a result, the study concentrates on the significance of learner motivation and teaching resources in learning a foreign language.

Keywords: foreign language, English language, motivation, teaching materials, podcasts, educational apps.

Introduction. One of the most crucial elements in language acquisition has been identified as motivation, which is the second highest predictor of language learning success after aptitude [2, 49]. It mainly results in a clear objective, behavioral changes (a desire to please parents through personal accomplishments, different productive study habits), a strong desire to reach the objective, and other attitudes.

Susan further assumed that motivation is a function of time and success; in other words, motivation is not constant and changes with time. Sometimes changes are necessary to achieve success. As a result, it may involve a few stages, including the preactional stage, which encourages people to choose an objective, the actional stage, which keeps people motivated despite obstacles, and the postactional stage, which wraps up the efforts and evaluates the outcomes [3, 98-99]. I. Zimney argues that "the communicative purpose communicates what communicative objective is pursued by the speaker planning some type of influence on the listener, but the motive is what explains the nature of the provided speech action." [5].

The ability to stay focused and behave appropriately while also giving kids the extra energy they need to complete activities is known as motivation. As a result, it can support activities for a while [4, 93-122]. The impact of motivation on a student's behavior, preferences, and performance in the classroom can take many different forms. For example, motivation can help us focus our attention on the tasks that need to be completed, enable us to complete these tasks more quickly while still maintaining our attention for a longer period of time, reduce distractions and better withstand them, affect the amount of information we retain and store, affect how easy or difficult tasks seem to us at the time.

The ability to support learning can be found in many forms and sizes of teaching materials. Making lessons engaging, facilitating learning, and enabling teachers to clearly communicate concepts are the goals of teaching and learning materials [1, 67-70]. It's time to provide examples of different types of language teaching resources now:

Podcasts. A wide range of excellent resources for language study may be accessed with the click of a link or the press of a button thanks to podcasts. Regardless of the provider you

select, they can deliver an outstanding selection of content in several languages on a wide range of subjects, including music, sports, and movies.

Educational apps. The majority of podcast listeners access their favorite episodes via a mobile phone app, and teachers can choose from a wide variety of different apps to complement their instruction. Apps and other digital teaching aids can engage students who are familiar with technology effectively and give you more teaching options.

Games and tests. Language teachers can make their own games and tests for students to take either online or in the classroom using a variety of free web tools. A contemporary, digital means to test vocabulary, phrases, and idioms is provided by well-known programs like Kahoot and Quizlet. There are hundreds of games created by other educators that you may easily use or adapt, and educators can also share their own games. Students log in with a code or through an app after the teacher creates and publishes the quiz session. Students of various ages can play on mobile phones individually or in groups, striving for the greatest score.

Conclusion. Children and young people who are motivated are better able to concentrate on a main objective or result. By doing this, they become unaffected by potential distractions and are able to focus for extended stretches of time. Pupils that are driven exhibit behavior that is goal-oriented. They demonstrate initiative, resiliency, control their curiosity, care about their work, and appreciate it. As for the sources of the language-learning process, they are thought to be the instructional materials. The provided teaching resources are helpful for students as they learn a foreign language.

References:

1. Brown, H. Douglas. (2000). Teaching by Principles. An Interactive Approach to Language Pedagogy. Second Edition. New York: Pearson Education
2. Dornyei Z. "Motivation in second and foreign language learning". Cambridge University Press, 1998
3. Gass M.S and Selinker L. "Second language acquisition". Routledge, 2008
4. Wachob, P. (2006). Methods and materials for motivation and learner autonomy Reflections. English Language Teaching, Vol. 5(1): 93-122
5. Зимняя И. А. – Психологические аспекты обучения говорению на иностранном языке – М.: Просвещение, 1978.